

Combinatorial Geometric Series

Chinnaraji Annamalai
School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India
Email: anna@iitkgp.ac.in
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0992-2584>

Abstract: This paper presents a geometric series with binomial coefficients or a combinatorial geometric series. The binomial coefficient of combinatorial geometric series is different from the traditional binomial coefficient.

MSC Classification codes: 05A10, 40A05 (65B10)

Keywords: computation, combinatorics, binomial coefficient

1. Introduction

Combinatorial geometric series [1-4] is produced by multiple summations of a geometric series as follows:

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i. \text{ Here, } \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \text{ is the combinatorial geometric series.}$$

The binomial coefficient of combinatorial geometric series is given below:

$$V_r^n = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)(r+3) \cdots (r+n)}{n!}, (n \geq 1, r \geq 0 \text{ \& } n, r \in N),$$

where $N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ is set of natural numbers including zero element

The traditional binomial coefficient denotes $\binom{n}{r} = \frac{n!}{r!(n-r)!}$, where $n, r \in N$.

Let us compare the binomial coefficient V_x^y with the traditional binomial coefficient:

Let $z = x + y$. Then, $\binom{z}{x} = zC_x = \frac{z!}{x!y!}$. Here, $V_x^y = V_y^x \Rightarrow zC_x = zC_y, (x, y, z \in N)$.

For example, $V_3^5 = V_5^3 = (5+3)C_3 = (5+3)C_5 = 56$.

Also, $V_n^0 = V_0^n = nC_0 = nC_n = \frac{n!}{n!0!} = 1$ and $V_0^0 = 0C_0 = \frac{0!}{0!} = 1 (\because 0! = 1)$.

2. Binomial Expansion

The following binomial identity [1, 2] is created using the binomial coefficients of the combinatorial geometric series.

$$V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + \cdots + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1} \text{ and } V_n^0 + V_n^1 + V_n^2 + \cdots + V_n^r = V_{n+1}^r, (\because V_n^r = V_r^n).$$

From the binomial identity $V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + \cdots + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1}$, we can derive the following binomial expansions:

$$(1). \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^0 = \sum_{i=0}^n 1 = 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + \dots + 1 + 1 = \frac{(n+1)}{1!}.$$

$$(2). \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^1 = \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(i+1)}{1!} = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots + n + (n+1) = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)}{2!}.$$

$$(3). \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^2 = \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(i+1)(i+2)}{2!} = 1 + 3 + \dots + \frac{(n+1)(n+2)}{2!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)}{3!}.$$

$$(4). \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^3 = \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3)}{3!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)}{4!}.$$

$$(5). \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^4 = \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3)(i+4)}{4!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5)}{5!}.$$

Similarly, we can continue this process up to r times. The r^{th} binomial expansion is as follows:

$$(r). \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r = \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3) \dots (i+r)}{r!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2) \dots (n+r)(n+r+1)}{(r+1)!},$$

From the binomial identity $V_n^0 + V_n^1 + V_n^2 + \dots + V_n^r = V_{n+1}^r$, we can derive the following binomial expansions.

$$1 + \frac{(n+1)}{1!} + \frac{(n+1)(n+2)}{2!} + \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)}{3!} + \dots + \frac{(n+1)(n+2) \dots (n+r)}{r!} \\ = \frac{(n+2)(n+3) \dots (n+r)(n+r+1)}{r!}.$$

3. Conclusion

In this article, a combinatorial geometric series or geometric series with binomial coefficients has been developed using the multiple summations of a geometrics series. The idea is a sort of methodological advance which is useful for researchers working in science, economics, engineering, computation, and management.

References

- [1] Annamalai, C. (2020) Optimized Computing Technique for Combination in Combinatorics. *HAL* 02865835. <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02865835>.
- [2] Annamalai, C. (2020) Novel Computing Technique in Combinatorics. *HAL* 02862222. <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02862222>.
- [3] Annamalai, C. (2022) Annamalai's Binomial Identity and Theorem. *SSRN* 4097907. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4097907>.
- [4] Annamalai, C. (2022) My New Idea for Optimized Combinatorial Techniques. *SSRN* 4078523. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4078523>.